

Review Article

Impacts of Social Media on Mental Health

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ABSTRACT

The intricate relationship between social media use and youth mental health is examined in this study. The results, which demonstrate both positive and negative effects, emphasize the need for informed digital participation. Knowing aid in creating strategies for maximizing and minimizing the potential of social media. **Material and methodology** - This study involved a diverse group of 175 people aged between 15 and 35. The research method for data collection included social media activity analysis, In-depth interviews and surveys, gather comprehensive information regarding trends in social media use, indices of mental health and the perceived effects analysis. The analysis phase incorporated with the objective of identifying risk variables, protective factors and relationships within a data, providing a holistic understanding of the complex interplay between social media and the mental wellbeing of young adults. **Result and conclusion**- There was a correlation between increasing symptoms of anxiety, depression and excessive use of social media, moderating effects can be obtained from positive interactions and instructional content. In conclusion, the impact of social media on youth's mental health, as highlighted by the drug surveillance approach, raises awareness of the potential negative psychological effects of excessive social media use on their well-being. This understanding could lead to the development of targeted interventions and programs to help mitigate these effects and promote healthy online practices. These insights can also help shape policies and guidelines to protect youth's mental health in this digital era.

INTRODUCTION

A social media is an online platform which people use to build social networks or social relations with other people who share similar personal or career interests, activities, backgrounds or real-life connections. The impact of social networks on young people is significant. Instagram, Snapchat,

Facebook, WhatsApp, Twitter(X). These websites are used -extensively over the globe for a variety of purposes, and in recent years social media usage is significantly increased by the teenagers many people believe that their day is lacking if they don't scroll past their social media accounts because it

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has also become a vital activity for grownups. Communication is now simpler as a result. Additionally, social media makes it simple to share images, communicate via messages and other forms of data, express ideas, and see movies from around the globe. [1]

In 2023, an estimated 4.9 billion people use social media across the world. With 4.9 billion users worldwide, social media usage has reached a new high. Furthermore, it is anticipated that by 2027, this number will increase to 5.85 billion users. These aren't platform-specific users, either: the requirement for a multi-platform approach to social media marketing is highlighted by the fact that the average user now disseminates their digital footprint across an astounding six to seven platforms each month.

According to data from the largest social media sites, there were 398.0 million users in India who were 18 years of age or older at the beginning of 2023, or 40.2 percent of the whole population of the nation. In India in January 2023, 67.5% of all internet users (regardless of age) used at least one social networking site. The most widely used social media platform in India in 2023 is Instagram, which has 74.70 percent of the country's internet users. In India, there are approximately 516.92 million users of Instagram who are active daily. Instagram's user base is largely made up of young people, especially teenagers. Youth have had a significant impact from social media in both positive and negative ways. It's critical to understand that the consequences might vary greatly according to usage

habits, age, and other factors. Most common negative impact of social media is its excessive usage in the individuals of age varying from 7-35yrs of age including both males and female. The average total screen time in India is 7hours 18min, and mobile screen time is 4hours 5min, as per 2023 data reports. Thus the occurrence of negative

impacts is more these days. In which the most common is the impact on mental health.

According to the record posted through Statista (Jan –2023), the most famous social media platforms are shown in figure 1 below. [10]

Figure 1: Showing the range of social media users global (in millions)

Mental health is a state of wellbeing where in the individual realize his or her on abilities can address the normal stress of existence can work productively and fruit fully and is able to make contributions to his or her community (world health organisation.Jun.04.2015.cited.18.07.2020) Mental health is defined as a kingdom of nicely-being wherein each man or woman realizes his or her personal capability, can deal with the everyday stresses of existence, can paintings productively and fruitfully, and is capable of make a contribution to her or his network (World Health Organization 2014a, 12).

Mental health is a fundamental and vital part of overall health. It may be described in 3 approaches: the absence of disorder, a state in which the organism lets in the overall performance of its characteristic, a country of stability between one's bodily and social environment. Each of these 3 definitions relies upon at the primary needs, inclusive of meals, safe haven, survival, protection, society, support and freedom from pain, environmental risks, and stress and from any

part of exploitation. (Bhangra, Till & Sartorius 2013, noted 18.07.2020)

Based on the above three definitions, it can be stated that mental health is a state of well-being and an ability to understand and make use of one's ability to stay a normal life. However, there are numerous arguments in finding the regularly occurring meaning of mental health.

Literature Review

This review will examine multiple scholarly articles regarding research found on the effects social media has on mental health. The literature reviewed here will help determine whether social media platforms, virtual realities and online gaming has a detrimental effect on the mental health of its users. In a study published by The International Journal of Indian Psychology, Hilal Bashar and Ahmad Bhat examined how social media's sporadic enhancement in quantity, quality and utility has caused great concern for parents, researchers and society regarding the mental health of individuals. The research focuses on how virtual life isolates individuals from other fellow beings, thereby affecting both mental and physical health, as well as overall balance. Various studies have reported a link between excessive social media use and compulsive disorder. One study revealed that forty five percent of British adults experience restlessness when they are not able to access their frequently used social networking sites (Anxiety 2012). It was also found that younger generations were found victim to Phantom vibration syndrome (PVS), which is nothing more than the perception of an addict person regarding the vibration of their cellphone (Drouin, et al., 2012; Rothberg, et al., 2010). Victims of PVS reflect an obsession of frequent checking of social messages, thus exhibiting anxiety. Amelia Strickland of University of Central Florida examined the impact of sedentary behaviors on mental health, displaced behavior, sleep interruption due to blue light exposure, and

social media's effect on romantic and platonic relationships of teens and young adults. Although social media is accessible to nearly anyone, young adults have been found to be the most active users. A study found that 84% of individuals ages 18-29 are on Facebook, more than any other age group (Smith 2013). Rapid task switching, or multitasking, which is encouraged by social media, has been linked to a root cause of depression in young adults. According to (Rosen et al., 2013), "While multitasking is inherently a human trait, technology has perhaps overly encouraged and promoted it by our multi-window computer environments, multi-app smartphone screens and the wide ranging sensory stimulation and distraction offered by high definition, customizable visual and auditory signals coupled with tactile stimulation through vibrations.

In a research study published by Sage Journals, Michelle O'Reilly and her fellow colleagues focused on how adolescents themselves perceive social media. Three themes were identified in a thematic analysis that suggested adolescents perceived social media as a threat to mental wellbeing, those being of which: (1) it was believed mood or anxiety disorders, (2) it was viewed as a platform for cyber bullying and (3) the use of social media was often framed as an addiction. A review of studies on cyber bullying showed a medium prevalence of 23%, with social media being the main platform (Hamm et al., 2015). A commentary published by the American Journal of Pharmaceutical Education studied the overall student health and wellness in higher education. Pharmacy and other health professions colleges in particular have recognized that well-being is important for students preparing for high-stress health care careers. This awareness has prompted universities and colleges to proactively address risk factors for stress, depression and anxiety, and educate students about

the importance of sleep, nutrition, exercise and hobbies.

Eiser, a prominent “generations” researcher, connects the growing demands for “safe spaces” and campus speech restrictions to a generation who communicates and socializes primarily online. She explains that most of the “threats” this generation has received have come through social media and texts, and therefore, they are more likely to associate “words” with violence.

Although social media holds a negative connotation to its effects on mental health, there are a few positives that it holds. Munmun De Choudhury of the Georgia Institute of Technology and Sushovan De of Arizona State University examined a highly popular social news and entertainment media site, Reddit. It is relatively different from Facebook, Instagram and Twitter(X). Reddit takes on the format of a forum, rather than a person blog. This study found that reddit users in the mental health community forums share quite explicit information about mental health issues. The use of throwaway accounts in the subreddits that they studied indicates that the feature of anonymity allows users to express their views and thoughts relatively freely. This is something that may be viewed as extreme or unacceptable to the mainstream. The anonymity feature allows users to feel more comfortable expressing personal details and allows them to release some stress they may be holding in. They can also chat with others online for comfort who may share the same feelings. Also many health professionals reply to questions or concerns one may have. Social media also gives teens and young adults a platform to post about a range of topics such as their accomplishments, future goals and aspirations, or even their family playing an especially prominent role. In a survey conducted in 2018 on “Teens’ Social Media Habits and Experiences”, it was found that 49% of teens so they post their accomplishments and 44% post

about the family. Social media also has 17 humility to connect with others and share their lives through Photos videos and status updates. Teams generally believe social media helps them deepen friendships and connect with others.

And a study at the University of Pittsburgh, it was found that there was a correlation between time spent on social media apps and negative body image feedback. Teens who had spent more time on social media had 2.2 times the risk of reporting eating and body image concerns, compared to others who spent less time on these platforms.

Many parents' concerns with social media are that it would affect their children's performance in school. The desire for instant gratification is seen as a negative impact that these online platforms can have on sleep and sleep quality in teens and adolescence. Data from qualitative studies have shown that when using social media compulsively, it can damage sleeping patterns. The University of Glasgow found that young people found it difficult to relax following night time social media views, reducing their brains ability to prepare for sleep.

IMPACTS OF SOCIAL MEDIA ON MENTAL HEALTH

In the subsequent bankruptcy, the impact of social media is divided into classes: Positive impacts and negative impacts.

Positive Impacts:

Some of the blessings of social media on intellectual fitness are discussed beneath in short:

a) Mental health support

Social media can provide mental health assist. “It has immediacy for buying support whilst we need it most, and there may be no one around, or no one we experience we can visit with our troubles (a common revel in among people with intellectual fitness problems is one of the emotions: burden to others)”, said Katie Sutton who is the student Nursing Times editor for Mental Health branch. In her weblog she gave an instance of a nurse-

maiden, Sally-Ann who published on Twitter at 11:20 pm as comply with:

“My daughter is having an excessive panic assault, we r using a paper bag, however I can't appear to settle her? She is so scared it's terrible any recommendation?”

The tweet above got the eye of the several nurses providing advice and retweeting it. Sally-Ann twitted after 20 minutes pronouncing her daughter is feeling better and thanked all of the pointers she acquired. (Sutton 2013, Cited 22.07.2020.)

Nowadays not every person use social media as a platform to connect to pals and household, however there are also many specialists who are giving advice and inspiration to the needy human beings thru it. In the case of intellectual health, folks that be afflicted by a few mental health troubles inclusive of anxiety, and depression, some locate it hard to proportion their troubles with the actual humans round them. In such cases, social media plays a supportive role to connect such a person to be seeking for help from unique fitness professionals or human beings with similar experiences clearly. For instance, elefriends is a social platform managed by the intellectual fitness charity (Mind) which offers urgent help at the intellectual fitness issues. There are also numerous community pages or companies in Facebook run by using mental fitness experts to assist intellectual fitness problems and to increase focus. Instagram gives aid and enables while kind '#depressed' in a seek container. However, the user need to also be chargeable for choosing the precise structures to proportion their problems because social media is also an area in which on-line bullying happens all the time. In a brand new survey supported by Hope lab and Well Being Trust, it demonstrated that social media is a fundamental part of younger human being's lives and that massive quantity of teens and adults experiencing moderate to severe signs and symptoms of depression turn to the internet for

assist. The survey file even alerted telling younger people who've signs of despair to stay off the social media might not continually be smart; for some, it can reduce off an important lifeline, a connection to advice, facts, inspiration, and help. (Miller 2018, Cited 25.07.2020.)

b) Personal Empowerment:

Social media provide quite a number advantages and possibilities to empower humans in an expansion of methods. It plays the function of a writer, curator, and spectator. In greater detail, thru social media, a person can create their profile displaying their exceptional first-rate, share the profile with billions of audiences from around the world and seek for the proper possibility. The social media is a place of understanding from in which human beings can research the talents they are interested in, read and comply with the inspiring stories of a successful character, get influenced and develop as an assured individual. Further, in a weblog written by way of Tazi, she referred to an Australian version who quitted using social media with the aid of describing them inauthentic and useless. However, Tazi was no longer convinced with that action and the reason she gave describing social media as meaningless. Instead, Tazi said, “social media gives representation unparalleled in mainstream media.” (Tazi 2015, Cited 05.08.2020.) Social media is accessible to all and sundry round the arena. The position of social media on social reformation is incomparable. Through social media terrible practices are shared, listened and were given helped. It has emerged as a place to shout out. Today, the third gender are using social media to connect human beings like them in subsequent corner of the world, and fat ladies are inspiring others to wear something they need freely, black women and men are speak me approximately racial injustices, and deprived human beings are motivating others via their paintings regardless of bodily weak spot. Such sports in social media are

empowering people in exclusive components of the sector and make them feel that they're no longer by myself.

Negative Impacts:

Some of the huge poor influences of social media on intellectual health are mentioned under:

a) Cyberbullying:

Bullying is any undesirable competitive behaviour(s) in the direction of young people by some other young people or group of youths, who are not siblings or modern relationship companions, concerning an found or perceived electricity imbalance (CDC, 2018, Cited:.06.08.2020). Online bullying permits perpetrators the effective advantage of anonymity. When afforded the capability to cover at the back of a computer display screen, perpetrators act without regard for the outcomes and experience much less accountability and guilt for their actions (Moreno & Strasburg 2014a,55). The worst of cyberbullying is it could appear whenever, anywhere publicly or privately. This sort of merciless practices in social media has an instantaneous effect at the psychological fitness of a targeted man or woman which can result in the incorrect selection of committing suicide within the worst scenario.

In detail, one observe surveyed university college students on how frequently they had skilled digital bullying behaviours and discovered that 38% knew a person who had been cyberbullied, 21.9% had been cyberbullied, eight.6% had acted as a cyberbully (Moreno & Strasburg 2014b, fifty six & fifty seven). Cyberbullying causes the feeling of loneliness, low self-esteem, suicidal ideation, increase social anxiety and melancholy. Likewise, emotional distress, anger, sadness, detachment, externalized hostility, and delinquency is likewise the signs visible in cyberbullied character. The famous social media platform which includes Facebook, Twitter, Instagram, and YouTube are in which cyberbullying is broadly practiced.

For example, Amanda Todd, 15 years vintage, became a Canadian teen who posted a video on YouTube sharing her reviews on bullying both online and in college. In the video, she told a story of the way she suffered from the depression and tension with the collection of white playing cards. She needed to alternate the college a couple of times, however the bullying persevered. After posting the video on YouTube, she committed suicide in 2012. That incident got the eye of the news media globally. (NG, 2012a, Cited 13.10.2018.)

b) Social media Addiction

The problem of social media addiction has become a global problem in the present era. Social media platforms like galaxy; each day we learn a little extra about it, and every day it movements a chunk in addition away (Jacobson 2009, 13). Social media have been advanced to provide a platform for verbal exchange in its preliminary degree. Now they provide such a lot of functions that it has turn out to be hard to live away from them. In one manner or different, humans are related to social media. The excessive use of social media in cutting-edge society has created a new hassle: the trouble of addiction. Social media addiction is becoming very serious and has equated with addictions to difficult tablets like heroin and crack cocaine (Woods 2014, Cited 08.08.2020).

Furthermore, studies has discovered out that certain sports in social media such as texting and getting a respond, getting likes, notifications and nice feedback, releases a chemical 'dopamine' produced via the mind which could be very addictive. Dopamine is the same chemical that makes sense true whilst we smoke, drink and gamble. So, social media provide the same level of pleasure as tablets and gambling that maintain customers to involve in social media activities time and again. This is why the object of dependency turns into extra critical to an addict

than something of their lives (C. Nakeya 2015, 13 & 14).

Such addiction has an instantaneous effect on mental health. Addicts have low self-esteem, feeling of envy, anxiety, napping sickness and inside the worst situation, they commit against the law. There are a number of terrible incidents round the arena due to social media addiction.

c) Depression, Anxiety and low self-esteem:

Depression is a common mental disorder that causes humans to revel in depressed mood, loss of interest or delight, feeling of guilt or low self-esteem, disturbed sleep or urge for food, low power and negative attention (Mental Health Foundation 2018, Cited 25.07.2020). Likewise, Anxiety is a sort of worry normally associated with the notion of a threat or something going incorrect in the future however also can arise from something going on right now (Mental Health Foundation 2018, Cited 25.07.2020). The dating among depression, tension, and occasional vanity are inter-related. They can appear at any time, everywhere and from something. Recently, immoderate use of social media is observed to be a critical purpose of depression and tension.

In a survey carried out by means of Dr. Heather Cleland Woods at Glasgow University, 467 teenagers were puzzled on their ordinary and night-time social media use. The end result revealed that common social media use, night time-time precise use and emotional funding all had a significant impact on best of sleep connected with the better degree of depression and anxiety. Similarly, a have a look at of 700 secondary college students in Ottawa discovered that folks who use social community sites have poor intellectual health three times more than folks who don't use them. (Levy 2015, Cited 27.07.2020.)

The reasons of melancholy and anxiety amongst people are numerous depending at the belief of the human beings in the direction of social media. Fear of Missing out (FOMO) is one of the reasons

humans use social media nowadays. FOMO manner fear of missing out among the institution of friends, families and precise unions. It is likewise a worry of being neglected. FOMO preserve customers coming back to social media repeatedly that could even result in dependency after which to despair. Checking messages regularly even when there aren't any messages, preserving an eye at the notification bar all the time are the signs and symptoms of FOMO.

d) Student as a sufferer:

In the record "Students' Online Usage: Global Market Trends Report" published by way of Monica Jannuzzi and Laura Bridge stock in 2013, a complete of 918 surveys were completed at QS World Grad School Tour activities held in 26 international locations across Europe, Asia, Latin America, North America, and Africa. The record cantered on net usage tendencies of modern-day and Potential students global overlaying especially three areas: Time spent online, Internet device utilization, Global social community alternatives. The findings on Time Spent Online and Social Networks from the record are supplied below:

• Time Spent online

Time spent online in keeping with day by students of all age companies are zero-three hours.

Those college students who're interested by engineering & generation reported to spend 5+ hours on line in keeping with day.

In India, Latin America and Africa, respondents are much more likely to file 5+ hours on line in an afternoon.

Social Networks: In all-location (Europe, Asia, Latin America, North America, Africa), extra than 50% students are mentioned to apply 5 key networks which include Facebook, Twitter[X], YouTube, WhatsApp, and Instagram all the time. The number one motivation for social media utilization in all area is to stay up to date. However, in Latin America, college students use social

media due to their hobby. Same situation is seen in India too.

SURVEY AND RESULTS

An online questionnaire survey using [Google forms] was conducted through E mail, WhatsApp and also link shared via Facebook, Instagram

received valuable feedback. A total of 175 participants ranging from the ages of 18 to 35 were recorded in the survey questionnaire in online survey.

The survey questions are in Appendix 1.

1 How many hours per day do you spend on social media?

174 responses

2. Do you feel that social media affects your mental health?

174 responses

3. Have you ever felt anxious or depressed after using social media?

174 responses

4. Have you ever experienced cyberbullying or negative comments on social media?

174 responses

5. Do you think that social media fosters unrealistic standards of beauty and success for young people?

172 responses

6. How do you think social media affects relationships between young people?

174 responses

7. Do you think that social media's effects on youth should be monitored and studied?

174 responses

8. Have you ever found yourself comparing your life to others' online profiles?

173 responses

9. Do you think social media can be a platform for positive social change?

174 responses

10. How do you think social media companies can better protect young users from negative experiences?

172 responses

CONCLUSION AND DISCUSSION

There are both types of the impact of the use of social media on mental health: positive and negative. The purpose of this thesis became to encourage the students to use social media platforms in a balanced way. Using social media in a balanced manner fosters the wellbeing of a person. It was essential to aware the students about the possible positive and negative impacts of

social media on their mental health. Before that, it was also important to recognize the understanding of the students about the outcomes of social media on mental health. Therefore, the online questionnaire survey was carried out via e mail, WhatsApp and link shared through Facebook and Instagram. The favoured social media platform for maximum of the students are located to be Instagram Facebook, YouTube, Twitter[X], and

Whatsapp. However, there were also students who had mental illness while using social media platform. Majority of the students are aware about the negative consequences of social media. Only some students are unaware of the effects of social media on their mental health. Considering those students who don't have any idea at the results of social media on their intellectual health, the thesis provides them with enough records on the brilliant and dark aspect of social media. Based on the research element, the fantastic impacts of social media may be non-public empowerment, the premise for intellectual fitness assist, and feeling of belongingness. The poor outcomes are cyberbullying, social media dependency, depression, anxiety, and low self-esteem. The thesis supposed always to promote tremendous aspects of social media on mental health. The students who do not know social media usage effects, this thesis may be a package which inspires them to use social media competently and productively. For students who are already aware of the effects of social media on their mental health, this thesis can expand their knowledge-how to farthest. The positive and negative influences of social media on mental health are mentioned and explained within the research part. In the empirical part, survey was conducted through the Google form. Among 175 respondents, the daily average spending time on social media turned into more than four hours. While the usage of social media, the purpose of the respondents was communication, education, entertainment, marketing, and networking respectively. On concerning whether social media is helpful or not to the students, the opinions are diverse. Through social media, some students have even provided mental health support whereas others yet don't know to help and to get help. Before researching on the topic, I thought there could be many positive aspects of social media on mental health. However, after research, the

perception has changed and determined extraordinary. Along with the fantastic factors of social media on mental health, there are numerous negative consequences. Now, the challenge to the users of social media is to exercise secure social. To exercise secure social, sufficient information on deciding on the proper social media platform, their motive of the usage of social media, privacy laws, limitations of social media web sites, and social skills are keys. However, the lack of education on social media usage and its consequences is making the situation complicated every day increasing the quantity of mental health patients.

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APPENDICES

The survey consists of following questions;

1. How many hours per day do you spend on social media?

- A) Less than 1 hour
- B) 1-2 hours
- C) 2-3 hours
- D) 3-4 hours
- E) More than 4 hours

2. Do you feel that social media affects your mental health?

- A) Yes
- B) No
- C) Not sure

3. Have you ever felt anxious or depressed after using social media?

- A) Yes
- B) No
- C) Not sure

4. Have you ever experienced cyber bullying or negative comments on social media?

- A) Yes
- B) No
- C) Not sure

5. Do you think that social media fosters unrealistic standards of beauty and success for young people.

- A) Yes
- B) No
- C) Not sure

6. How do you think social media affects relationships between young people?

- A) Improves them
- B) Harms them
- C) No effect
- D) Not sure

7. Do you think that social media's effects on youth should be monitored and studied?

- A) Yes
- B) No
- C) Not sure

8. Have you ever found yourself comparing your life to others' online profiles?

- A) Yes
- B) No
- C) Not sure

9. Do you think social media can be a platform for positive social change?

- A) Yes
- B) No
- C) Not sure

10. How do you think social media companies can better protect young users from negative experiences?

- A) More strict content moderation
- B) Improved reporting and action against cyber bullying
- C) Limiting usage time for young users
- D) All of the above
- E) Not sure